

Funding the social transformation of housing estates. Environmental ambitions as catalysers of the regeneration of Corviale

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Abstract

This study aims to unravel the dynamic interplay between new environmental considerations and the lifespan of housing estates within urban regeneration programs. Through a case study, the following contribution paper examines how the funding of urban regeneration projects has evolved and is today mobilised under the umbrella of just transition initiatives in the European context. This holds particular significance in the context of Southern European nations, which are key beneficiaries of the comprehensive recovery funding provided by the EU through initiatives such as the Next Generation EU funds. The study adopts sociotechnical methods to analyse the case of Corviale, a housing estate built for 8,500 residents in the outskirts of Rome, along with two main regeneration programs: the Contratto de Quartiere II and the Piano Urbano Integrato (PUI - PNRR).

Keywords

Urban regeneration, housing estates, demolition, climate change, social innovation

Housing estates regeneration in a climate crisis context

Although the challenge of governing large housing estates has been a concerning issue for some decades (Dekker et al., 2005), the new climatic regime raises (Latour, 2018) new challenges in their governance. Acknowledging that the environmental impact of transforming housing buildings is considerably lower than that of demolition (Power, 2008), different scholars (e.g. Lees, 2008) claim a transition to a model of sobriety that defends the practice of transformation over building new mass housing developments. Large housing estate regeneration initiatives are emerging, with a notable portion of these initiatives often receiving funding through programs with strong environmental ambitions (e.g. REHA program by the Ministry of Ecology of France, or the PUI-PNRR in Italy). This article delves into alternative modes of governing the transformation of housing estates by studying the opportunities that climate change politics can bring to the regeneration of such estates. The objective of this research is to analyse the nexus between the lifespan of housing estates and new environmental policies in the context of housing estate regeneration initiatives. The study explores this nexus through one case of housing estate regeneration in Southern Europe:

Corviale housing estate in the suburbs of Rome. Corviale had been thread with demolition in different moments of its history but is today engaged in a profound regeneration process.

The demolition of large housing estates spread in Europe during the 80s and 90s. The UK, France, and The Netherlands accumulate the largest rate of demolitions of housing estates in Europe (Thomsen & Van der Flier, 2006). In these countries, demolition is still an established practice (ibid.). As described by A. Berland-Berthon (2012) through the study of different demolition examples in France, housing demolition has been reshaped as a legitimate line of public action regarding the management of public housing stock, as it was integrated as a tool within the French Urban Renewal National Program in 2003. The demolition of housing estates has proved to be harmful to the mental health of the displaced community (Lees, 2008), and also to have environmental consequences. The recurrent critics against demolition, the scarcity of affordable housing in many European cities and the current climate crisis are factors that in the last two decades have started changing the approach to the maintenance of housing estates. Despite demolition is still a reality on many Western European countries, today large housing estate regeneration initiatives are on the policy agendas of Western European countries (Dekker et al., 2005). In South European countries such as Italy or Spain, demolishing public housing stock is less common. Situations of mismanagement and social unrest within Italian or Spanish public housing estates tend to be approached by either selling or abandoning the public housing estates (Belmessous et al., 2005, Bricocoli et al., 2021; Puccini, 2016).

While a large amount of literature studies the decay and regeneration process of housing estates from Western European countries (mostly the UK and the Netherlands), there is a lack of studies tracing similar processes in Southern Europe cases (Monclús & Díez Medina, 2016). This paper addresses this gap in the literature by examining the renewal process of a housing estate located in Italy. Additionally, building on the research of Simon Guy and Andrew Karvonen (2011), this paper enhances existing literature by employing sociotechnical approaches and methods to study the interplay between the physical features of the housing estate and the planning tools implemented along the renewal process.

Corviale is a housing estate in the outskirts of Rome, designed in 1975 and finally built in 1984 by the IACP (*Istituto Autonomo Case Popolari*)¹. Corviale is selected as a case study to investigate the nexus between the lifespan of the housing estate and new environmental policies in the context of housing estate regeneration due to the presence of a well-documented long-term transformation process. The study approaches Corviale as a context of contingency and political contestation, where the uncommon features of the place have left space for the rise of different forces on the site, leading to the expansion of its lifespan, and later to the

¹ The IACP was a public Italian company for the development and management of public housing. The company's roman section is currently known as ATER (Azienda Territoriale per l'Edilizia Residenziale).

development of top-down social innovations initiatives, financed with the support of two regeneration programs with environmental budget.

This article is divided into seven sections. After this first section presenting the main issues and objectives of the research, the paper reports on the methodology followed through the study. In the third and four sections, the study analyses the features of Corviale: its outstanding proportions, its long corridors, its standardised constructive system. Then the study explores the local context through the relation between these physical characteristics and social context²: the extensive networks of actors engaged in its governance, the active participation of local associations, the work of community groups and the notoriety of the housing estate, that goes beyond the scope of the neighbourhood. In the fifth and sixth section, the study focuses on the evolution of the housing estate through the live cycle method, delving into what contributed to potentially increasing or reducing the lifespan of the housing estate. Finally, the seventh section examines how specific social conflicts are addressed through regeneration programs with environmental budgets, which modify particular physical features of Corviale and promote government-led social innovation initiatives.

The study is attentive to the endogenous and exogenous factors of the housing estate that have conditioned the governance of Corviale by tracing, with a socio-technical approach³, the influence of the physical conditions of the housing estate in the evolution of its governance process, leading to the extension of its lifespan. Additionally, this study posits that the local characteristics of Corviale and the regeneration programs with environmental budget have provided an alternative scenario favourable to the development of government-driven social innovation initiatives at Corviale, that have contributed to ensuring the regeneration of the neighbourhood.

Methodology, from the micro-scale to the grid

This study uses qualitative methods to collect and analyse data on the operationalisation of the regeneration project in Corviale. This article relies on some of the data and findings from a one-year research, which involved a 4-month field mission in Rome. The access and contact to the group of researchers of the Lab. Città Corviale helped define Corviale as a main case study, and has provided great access to primary data.

² For social context this article intends the extensive networks of actors engaged in its governance, the active participation of the local community and the notoriety of the housing estate, that goes beyond the scope of the neighbourhood. However, it must be noted that this article has only approached a section of the full complexity of the social groups that, through the 40 years of Corviale, have been involved in the governance process of the housing complex.

³ This sociotechnical approach is based in the work of Guy & Karvonen (2011), who describe for such an approach a way of studying technical objects as technologies that are inseparable from developments in the social sphere. The sociotechnical approach requires the analysis of the interaction of such technologies with a broad range of social actors, including scientists, engineers, policymakers, politicians, activists, artists, and users.

The process of data collection followed a three-part methodology. First, it involved a literature search, combining both general academic literature on housing estate governance and sociological studies of Corviale (e.g. del Monaco 2006, Di Giovanni 2022, Clough Marinaro 2021), with all the official documents related to the regeneration of the building and the review of academic work on the regeneration of Corviale (e.g. Calzado, 2023; Caudo, 2022; Di Giovanni, 2020). Specifically, the study of the regeneration programs of Corviale involved the analysis of the original briefs of the program, the study of funding structures and governance of the program, and the review of the environmental dimensions of each program.

Secondly, the study relied on primary data, based on observations on the use of the public space of Corviale, in neighbourhood meetings and official group meetings with social workers, and 25 interviews conducted with the different actors of Corviale such as interviews at a municipal level (policymakers and politicians, senior city officials), at the housing authority level (board members, operations managers, security personnel), and at the inhabitant's level (association leaders, long-term inhabitants, local social workers or informal occupants).

Finally, secondary data, such as former surveys and data provided from the Lab. Città Corviale was used *a posteriori* to complement and triangulate information gathered through the interviews and the observations. For that, a coding process was developed using the text analysis software Quirkos. This process helped to combine the secondary and the primary data, by organizing the data efficiently using a coding grid. This method was used to study the relationship between the local characteristics of Corviale (its local governance dynamics and physical features) and the development of two regeneration programs, the Contratto de Quartiere II, approved in 2003 and the Piano Urbano Integrato (PUI - PNRR) approved in 2022.

The study aligns with sociotechnical research methods (Guy & Karvonen, 2011; Wassenberg, 2013) that specify how such relations cannot be traced according to traditional methods of analysing the decision-making and the way power is distributed in housing estates governance and requires a new sociotechnical approach. This approach integrates the physical characteristics of a place within a classic governance analysis, that studies the actors, the objectives of these actors and their instruments (Lascoumes & Le Gales, 2007). This analysis draws on the comparison of the lifespan of buildings to that of living beings (Lönberg-Holm & Carl Theodore, 1953, Straub, 2001). This method allows to study the decision-making process within the governance of housing estate and distinguish with precision the factors that have contributed to potentially enlarging or reducing the lifespan of the building. The life cycle method provides a sociotechnical framework that allows mixing the social components of the governance of the building with the physical characteristics of the housing estate.

The main limitation of considering the Corviale neighbourhood as a single study case does not pertain to data scarcity; on the contrary, an excess of data exists, necessitating the arduous task of editing and elucidating the origins and authenticity of these data. The high amount of the myths surrounding the history of Corviale, and the large number of initiatives that were

eventually stopped without much administrative tracking in their operations complexified the search of veracious data. A second limitation of this study concerns time: the four-month fieldwork mission only allows for partial coverage of the numerous local initiatives organized by community groups over Corviale's forty years of inhabitation. Consequently, this article focuses solely on government-driven social innovation initiatives. The support of the researchers of the Lab. Città Corviale has been particularly important in this task, for identifying pertinent pieces of information that contribute to the construction of a compelling case.

Corviale case study

Corviale is a housing estate conceived by the IACP for 8500 inhabitants, built between 1975 and 1984, as a result of the PEEP I (Piano di Edilizia Economica e Popolare) of Rome, which aimed to resolve the post-war housing emergency that existed in Italy during the 1960s and 1970s (Di Giovanni 2019). Corviale is sometimes exclusively associated with its most recognisable element, an almost 1 km long high-rise housing slab. However, Corviale refers to a larger housing estate that includes three public housing buildings, the almost 1 km long building with apartments and a commercial floor that runs along the hill's ridge, a parallel lower building connected to the first one through several bridges, and a 250 metres long housing building, called the 'VI lot' located at a 45° angle (figure 1). Additionally, the housing estate is equipped with a circular one-way street that surrounds a large area with green spaces, civic, commercial, and cultural amenities, as well as a large Thermal Power Plant that provides heated water to the complex (Caudo, 2022).

1km of housing estate. Corviale's physical characteristics

Corviale's most recognisable volume is a housing building of 958 meters long block that rises to 30 meters. The dimensions of this building gain an even more monumental character as it is located on top of a ridge (Vidotto, 2017). The building comprises 11 levels, two underground and primarily designated for parking and storage. The remaining nine levels are above ground and intended for residential use, except for commercial space along the 4th and the 5th floor of the building, called the "Free floor" by the lead architect of Corviale, Mario Fiorentino, which separates the building horizontally into two blocks with two different types of apartments. The upper floors featured houses arranged along galleries and accessed by five primary staircases, while the lower floors contained in-line houses connected by secondary staircases.

Figure 1 - Bird eye view of the whole complex of Corviale. The image shows the 1Km long housing building, the VI lot situated at a 45-degree angle from the main structure, and portions of the public services. Furthermore, the image also depicts the adjacent countryside that begins just beyond Corviale. Source: Ater Roma

The building is divided transversely by five vertical elements where the stairwells and elevators are concentrated. Its structure runs uninterruptedly for almost a kilometre, except for a single disruption between the 2nd and 3rd stairwells to accommodate topographical changes. The layout of the building was designed to reproduce the mobility patterns of an urban system, separating different types of fluxes, such as the pedestrian or the vehicular flux, and including specific access points to the whole development. These access points are identifiable from the building's facade and coincide with the five primary stairwells. Fiorentino, Corviale's head architect, referred to these entry points and the open space in front as "true public squares" (Vidotto, 2017), giving again an urban character to the design of the building. In the words of the architect, the main building of Corviale was "not just a longer house: it is a 1 km system, highly integrated between services and residences, with distinct vehicular and pedestrian paths" (Mario Fiorentino, as cited in Del Monaco, 2006, p. 156). However, some consulted experts, members of the IACP, and neighbours during this research linked the distributive layout of Corviale to one of the biggest problems of the neighbourhood. The few entries to the building forced all the neighbourhoods to go through long corridors that were generally perceived as unpleasant, dark, and unsafe spaces⁴.

The decay process of Corviale. Occupation and stigma.

The example described in the previous section illustrates the contrast between the planners' initial intentions and what has taken place at Corviale. This continuous deviation

⁴ This feeling of insecurity in the corridors of Corviale was visible through the results of a survey conducted in the Elementary School of Corviale, where the pupils were asked to participate in drafting affectivity maps that linked their feeling in different parts of Corviale. These maps showed the concentration of dark dots along the ground floor corridor of Corviale, marking it as the most dangerous and ugliest part of the housing estate (Del Monaco, 2006).

from the planners' intentions is not unique to Corviale. Housing estate developed in the second half of the 20th century frequently experienced a mismatch between the architectural team's conceptual intentions and the actual results of their designs (Coleman, 1990). In the case of Corviale, Fiorentino and the rest of the architecture team were often blamed for having created an "Uncontrollable monster", a "prison-like building" that inevitably generated social difficulties (Vidotto, 2017). Taking some distance from the spatial deterministic approach of Coleman (1990), some academic studies on Corviale have linked the decay process of the housing estate to the IACP's management problems that emerged in the first years after the apartment assignments (e.g., Del Monaco, 2006; Giovanni, 2019; Puccini, 2016). Others have linked this decay to misfortune design decisions (Bartocci, 2016). An in-depth analysis of the different elements of the building (e.g. the long corridors, the heating system or the elevators) has shed light on the relation between the design of the building and the management decisions (Calzado, 2023), aligning with the theories of Wassenberg (2013) that established direct relations between larger governance dynamics of housing estates and their physical characteristics.

The following section explores the role of the physical features of Corviale influencing processes of physical decay and the development of social conflicts within the complex. Due to the pressing housing crisis in Rome that was still present during the early 1980s, the assignment process of the housing units of Corviale was initiated in 1982, two years before the end of the construction phase. The rough aesthetics of the complex together with its unfinished status quickly created an overall feeling of delusion and rejection among the assignee inhabitants (Campanella, 1995). In addition, the commercial and community services that were planned for being placed on the commercial floor of Corviale named the "Free floor" had not arrived, and the space left vacant was eventually informally occupied by different families. This occupation phenomenon also took place in other PEEP neighbourhoods in Rome, such as at Laurentino 38, where the buildings originally designed as bridge structures meant to have shops and offices for the neighbourhood were transformed into improvised shelters and eventually occupied on a permanent basis by families in search of housing (Caudo, 2022). Studies on the occupation of PEEP neighbourhoods have revealed that many families among the first occupiers had been affected by Law 392, also known as the Equo Canone Law, introduced in 1978 (Clough Marinaro, 2021). Despite the aim of this law to ensure fairer private rental prices, the Equo Canone led to numerous evictions and created a housing affordability crisis in Rome in the early 1980s (Ibid.). As was the case for many other PEEP housing estates, criminal networks often mediated in the occupation of the free floor, charging illegal renting fees to the occupants of these spaces. The occupation of the Free floor spanned over 30 years, drastically modifying the layout of the original project, as collective spaces were privatised, and the long walkable floor was turned into an inaccessible route. This occupation integrated new actors in the governance process of Corviale, such as the presence of illegal managers of the occupied apartments and the occupant residents of these apartments.

The coexistence of assignee residents and occupants created a conflict situation from the beginning. As explored by the sociologist Nicoleta Campanella (1995), the assignee residents would recurrently report these struggles to the IACP, who generally did not act upon it, inducing a degeneration of trust between the inhabitants and the housing authority (Ibid.). Numerous interviewees, comprising residents and housing authority members engaged in this research, correlated the housing authority's incapacity to address social concerns with its absence of an officially designated social support department. The IACP exclusively provides technical and administrative support to Corviale.

The lack of response from the housing authority prompted the inhabitants of Corviale to organise themselves and fight for their rights (Campanella 1995), resulting in a prolonged period of successful local bottom-up initiatives and collective reclamations of rights. The establishment of essential public services such as bus routes, schools, and healthcare centres has been attributed to the collective actions of these bottom-up initiatives, which were organised through spontaneous neighbourhood associations. The community of Corviale has long been engaged in a battle against sensationalized articles published by journalists, which contribute to the ongoing stigmatization of the building and its residents. In the early 2000s, this stigmatised image was instrumentalised by far-right-wing politicians and integrated into a political campaign that aimed at attracting votes from popular areas of Rome (Bonomo, 2021). These politicians asserted their support for the demolition of Corviale, initiating a debate that extends to the present day (Valeri, 2023).

Along this study, the interviews, the review of academic literature and of official documents have provided information that suggest a relationship between the physical characteristics of Corviale and the evolution of the social dynamics and local governance within the housing estate. Such is the case of the study of Clough Marinaro (2021) on the informal occupation of Corviale, and the result of the interviews to informal occupants and social workers at the housing estate developed for this study. The results of the analysis of both the literature and the interviews suggested that the existence of a large number of vacant commercial spaces within Corviale enabled the occupation of the 'Free floor' when the housing crisis in Rome hit even stronger after the passing of the *Equo Canone Law*. The 'Free floor' could be therefore considered as a physical element that interacted with a wide range of contextual factors, including social, cultural, and economic dynamics, promoting the decay process.

The monumental aesthetics associated with a socialist symbolic dimension of the building have also been analysed as an element that promoted the physical decay process of Corviale. Initially conceived during the rule of the *giunte rosse* (Left wing administrations) in Rome's municipal government, Corviale was eventually reframed by right wing parties who launched a campaign calling for its demolition, arguing that the building was the symbol of a flawed concept of the city rooted in left-wing utopian dreams. The relation between the monumental aesthetics of Corviale and the process of urban decay is traced through the analysis of media

reviews spanning from the 1980s to the present and delving into specific literature, such as Bruno Bonomo (2021) on the political life of Corviale or Vittorio Vidotto (2017) on the semiotics of Corviale allows to establish a relation between the monumental aesthetics of Corviale and the process of physical decay.

The regeneration projects of Corviale. Enlarging the lifespan of a housing estate

Almost parallel to the processes of physical decay and social conflicts that have endangered Corviale with the possibility of demolition, a regeneration process has taken place, pathing the way for a more optimistic future for the housing estate and the community. The results of the study of Corviale's physical elements trace the active role of some of these elements not only in the decay process but also in the decision-making process that influenced the regeneration of the housing estate (Calzado 2023). An example of this influence is the relation between the unordinary morphology of Corviale, which turned the building into subject of cultural interest, resulting in its submission under protection by the Roman urban regulation *Carta Per la Qualità* (Charter for Quality)⁵, which ensured its preservation. Another example of the relation between the physical elements of Corviale and the preservation of the building is the high density of apartments that exist in the main 1km building. As pointed out in an interview carried out for this research by the former director of the housing authority: *"The evaluation of demolition (...) was made only based on the political consequences of this choice. It means that if you decide to demolish Corviale, you get 4500 people in the middle of the street"*. The relocation of such a large number of inhabitants represented a complexity that influences the deviation of the political decision to demolish the structure.

This study oversees the two parallel processes that have contributed to expanding and reducing the life span of Corviale (figure 2). The lifecycle method (Thomsen & Van der Flier, 2006) consists of listing the main policies and events that have taken place at Corviale and organising them regarding whether they have contributed to potentially enlarging or reducing the lifespan of the building. The timeline presents the main physical transformation events, together with functional and (micro) economic performances (Van der Flier and Thomsen 2006) within the governance process of Corviale that have had an impact on the lifecycle of the building. The timeline is divided into two parts, the lower part studies the demolition-inducing events within the governance process of Corviale, and the upper part studies the transformation-inducing events.

⁵ Carta Per la Qualità is a document that protects the architectural heritage of Rome. This document does not explicitly forbid the demolition of Corviale but complexifies a potential demolition process of the housing estate, as any large intervention in Corviale, once enlisted in this chart, would require the revision and approval from the Sovrintendenza Capitolina (Rossi, 2003).

Figure 2. The life cycle of Corviale. Scheme of the main events and programs that have induced transformation or demolition. Source: Author's elaboration

Among the demolition-inducing events, this study gathers the main events that have accelerated the process of decay of the building, the main events that have contributed to the stigmatisation of the housing estate, and the direct propositions of demolition. As transformation-inducing events, this study gathers the direct transformation events and the main regeneration programs that have guided this transformation. Additionally, the study gathers the supra-national policies and measures, and heritage protection labels that complexify the demolition of Corviale by either making it more bureaucratic, or internationally well-known and part of a global debate.

Through this analysis we identify the two main regeneration plans that have contributed to enlarging the lifespan of Corviale. The two main plans are the Contratto di Quartiere II and the Piano Urbano Integrato Corviale. Under a top-down approach, these two urban renewal plans combine the integration of social innovation measures with environmental goals. Contratto di Quartiere II is a public initiative to regenerate Corviale approved by the Lazio Region through deliberations 574 and 922 in 2003 (Giovanni, 2019). The main objective of this initiative was to solve the informal occupation of the commercial spaces of the free floor, which had been transformed into private dwellings and occupied for more than 20 years. The program of the intervention was developed in a collaboration between public institutions (Lazio Region, Rome municipality), and the housing authority (ATER Roma, former Iacp). The designed intervention envisioned the punctual deconstruction of the self-built houses within the commercial spaces and the building of new public houses on the free floor to avoid forced evictions (Ibid.). This intervention would require the official change of use of the free floor, from a commercial area, into a residential area, which was approved in 2006. The project that emerged as the winner of implementing the intervention is known as Green Kilometre and is led by architect G. Salimei. At that time, the Municipality of Rome in collaboration with local grassroots initiatives of Corviale, created the Corviale Territorial Laboratory (Comune di Roma, 2005). This initiative had the aim of promoting forms of citizen participation and encouraging action for the enhancement of the environment and local development.

After years of stagnation, where the project seemed to have been abandoned, the Lazio Region allocated €10.5 million in 2019 for the implementation of the project. This project included demolishing and rebuilding the 120 self-built homes on the Free floor; retrofitting different areas of the building and including solar panels in one of the sections. In addition, the operation required the social support for the families being relocated. This support was appointed to a group of researchers from Roma Tre University, funding the Laboratorio di Città Corviale, with a similar role as the former Corviale Territorial Laboratory, by then dismantled. The Laboratory established a facility room onsite where they organised regular meetings with both the neighbourhoods, and the housing authority, mediating in the relation between both actors. The Lab. Città Corviale coordinated the reallocation of the families during the construction works in the free floor. The project in 2023 is ongoing, but some of the results of Phase 0 and Phase 1 are already visible.

The Piano Urbano Integrato (PUI) Corviale is a project funded by the Next Generation EU funds (NGEU). The NGEU is a European Union economic recovery package, approved in 2020 to support the EU member states in recovering from the COVID-19 pandemic (European Commission, 2021), from which Italy was the largest recipient. Italy's national government allocated these funds to the PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan). Among the various missions of the PNRR, mission 2 Green revolution and ecological transition received the highest percentage of funding (31.05%) (Ibid.). The Piano Urbano Integrato Corviale and two other Rome regenerations programs (Tor Bella Monaca and Santa Maria della Pietà) are framed under this mission (Osservatorio PNRR, 2023). The estimated amount to be allocated at Corviale is 50M euros. In Corviale, this funding is meant to be used for repeating a similar operation done on the *Free floor* at a smaller scale in the VI lot of Corviale (the building at a 45° degree), and for the development of some green areas around the housing buildings.

The Contratto di Quartiere II and the PUI of Corviale combined have mobilized over 60 million euros to regenerate various areas within Corviale. This sum is larger (proportionally) than any accumulation of investments in any other public housing estate in Rome. Consequently, the average investment per apartment in Corviale stands at 50,000 euros as a result of this funding. Considering that the cost of public housing construction in Italy is estimated to be around 1000 / 1200 euros per m², this investment could potentially fund the creation of a new housing development with a similar number of apartments (though smaller in size) as Corviale. This calculation is not mentioned in this article to argue that Corviale should not be renewed but to demonstrate the elevated investment committed to its renovation, to which different consulted experts have referred to as a disproportionate sum.

The following chart gathers the main details concerning both plans and allows for an easier comparison.

	Contratto di Quartiere II at Corviale	PUI 24 Polo della Solidarietà Corviale
Date of approval	2003	2022
General scope of the program	Contratto di Quartiere come from Italian Law 21/2001, art. 4 paragraph 1. They are regeneration programs no longer exclusively addressing physical degradation but also social degradation.	The PUI come from the Article 21, Decree-Law No. 152 of 6 November 2021. The primary objective of PUI plans are the ecological regeneration of existing building structures and public areas.
Environmental dimension of the program applied to Corviale plan	The official description of the program holds very light references regarding an environmental dimension. The only reference of the text mentions how “Contratti di Quartiere II” aimed at the redevelopment of buildings, the improvement of environmental conditions, the adaptation and development of urbanisation works and the provision of public and private services.	The environmental dimension is present along the whole document of Corviale. This environmental dimension is in line with the sustainability objectives of the PNRR, and with the DNSH of the EU taxonomy.
The other roman housing estates involved in this plan	Corviale, Primavalle-Torrevecchia, Tor Marancia, Quarticciolo,	Corviale, Tor Bella Monaca and Santa Maria della Pietà
Planned actions within the plan	The redevelopment of the 4th and 5th floors of the main building of Corviale, with a change of use from commercial to residential (to end the informal occupation of the free floor). The inclusion of educational, cultural, artistic and museum functions, and the completion and redevelopment of the public services of the 'Area Plan' (green areas, sports facilities, a play centre, and the Multipurpose Centre).	Renovation and energy efficiency of different buildings. Completion of a sports hall. Biodiversity recovery of the East and West Park. To that the project develops a series of intangible interventions for the promotion of social, cultural and economic activities and accompanying activities such as participatory processes and communication.
Budget of the plan	Total budget of the project at Corviale 10.580.729,40 euro. Most of these initiatives have a social regeneration scope. Of that budget, approximately a 9% was spent on initiatives with an environmental focus.	Total budget of the project at Corviale 50.043.779,00 euro. Most of these initiatives have an ecological scope. Of that budget, approximately a 4% is meant to be spent on initiatives with a social regeneration focus.

Actors engaged within the design and implementation of the plan	National government, Municipality of Rome, XV Municipality, ATER di Roma (housing authority), Regione Lazio. Additional actors such as local associations and universities are engaged in the development and implementation of different parts of the program. The programme is funded 65% by the State and 35% by the Region.	EU commission, National government, Municipality of Rome, ATER di Roma (housing authority), Regione Lazio. Additional actors such as local associations and universities are engaged in the development and implementation of different parts of the program. The program is funded 100% by the State.
Environmental actions developed for Corviale within this program	The retrofit of the new apartments of the free floor, the retrofit of the additional public service areas. Installation of photovoltaic panels.	Large scale retrofitting operations. Restauration of public green.
Added social dimension	<p>The "Corviale Territorial Laboratory, West Rome" was created by the Municipality of Rome, with the aim of promoting forms of citizen participation and encouraging action for the enhancement of the environment and local development. The participatory experience was active in the following years of the plan.</p> <p>However, the activity was abandoned in 2009, and only recovered in 2017, with the creation of the "Lab. Città Corviale", this time managed by University Roma Tre. The aim of such lab was to ensure the best possible involvement of the neighbourhood's inhabitants on the process of reallocation of the inhabitants of the free floor.</p>	<p>The plan designs the initiatives of urban regeneration parallelly to the community building experiences.</p> <p>The experience of community building is based in the accumulated knowledge from the work of researchers from the Lab. Città Corviale over the years of the Contratti di Quartiere II. In the case of the PUI, there is a specific budget within the plan dedicated for the activity of the Lab.</p>

Table 1 - Details of the Contratto di Quartiere II at Corviale and the PUI 24 Polo della Solidarietà Corviale

Environmental ambitions as innovation catalysers

Over the two decades separating the two plans, there has been a significant increase in global awareness regarding the pressing climate crisis. This heightened awareness has led to a greater political emphasis on incorporating ecological objectives into new urban transformation plans. The analysis of data from both plans further substantiates this idea, as it reveals a larger allocation of funding towards environmental initiatives in the case of the Piano Urbano Integrato (PUI) when compared to the Contratto di Quartiere II. In the case of "Contratti di Quartiere," the environmental dimension is closely integrated with other dimensions. In the case of " Piano Urbano Integrato", there seems to be almost exclusive attention to the ecological and environmental dimensions.

The growing significance of the environmental approach in Corviale's regeneration plans aligns with a worldwide trend of increasing awareness regarding environmental issues, which

has recently mobilized funding initiatives like the EU NextGeneration plan. In the case of Corviale, this approach also aligns with the intention to redefine the symbolic meaning associated with the building. In recent years, the semiotics of Corviale have been instrumentalised again by a political force, the left-wing Regional president Nicola Zingaretti, who has focused part of his political rhetoric in the recovery of the suburbs of Rome and has launched a campaign to enhance the sustainable dimension of Corviale. In public interventions Zingaretti described the recent transformation actions at Corviale as "the biggest green construction work of Europe". This strategy repeats the formula of reframing the symbolic meaning of Corviale that had been explored by the right-wing party between the 90s and the early 2000s, during the launch of the demolition campaign of Corviale (Bonomo 2021). As explored in the section 'The decay process of Corviale' (p.10), the symbolic meaning of Corviale is related to the physical and spatial characteristics of the building⁶ (Bonomo, 2021; Vidotto, 2017). The relation between the symbolic meaning of Corviale, framed now in sustainability terms, and the allocation of larger funds to finance the regeneration strategies of Corviale showcases the existing relationship between the local characteristics of Corviale and the regeneration programs with a robust environmental focus.

When comparing the environmental approach of both plans, we can observe how in the case of "Contratti di Quartiere," the environmental dimension is closely integrated with other dimensions, while in the case of "PUI," there is almost exclusive attention to the environmental dimensions. The Contratto Quartiere II predominantly adopts a social approach, with minimal emphasis on environmental activities, which receive only a small portion (9%) of the total budget for funding. On the other hand, the PUI places the environmental approach as its central pillar, allocating a mere 4% of activities for the social approach. Instead, the program prioritizes retrofitting and greening activities throughout the complex. However, the data indicates that the 4% allocated to social matters in the PUI plan is greater than the 91% dedicated to social matters in Contratto di Quartiere II. The data presented supports the hypothesis that environmental programs have the potential to foster social innovation by attracting substantial investments.

Examining the data from both plans also unveils the involvement of distinct actors engaged in the governance process. In particular the presence of EU-level administration, which on one hand possesses the capacity to finance significant projects, while on the other hand, imposes specific guidelines regarding the allocation of funds, as evidenced in the Allegato Piano Integrato Corviale (Regione Lazio, 2022). Additionally, the plans have promoted the existence of new intermediary groups such as the "Corviale Territory Laboratory" and the "Lab. Città Corviale".

⁶ For example, the monumental aesthetics of Corviale were associated with a socialist symbolic dimension (see page.10).

In the context of Corviale, intermediary groups played a crucial role in compensating for the historical lack of social support provided by the housing authority IACP to this neighbourhood, as highlighted by experts consulted for this study. These groups are either bottom-up initiatives, such as local associations, which have a long history of community work at Corviale, or government-driven groups, such as "Corviale Territory Laboratory" and the "Lab. Città Corviale". The role of intermediary actors within transition processes is approached in the study of Kivimaa et al. (2019) '*Passing the baton: How intermediaries advance sustainability transitions in different phases*'. Their research overviewed the different functions of intermediary actors within transitions and concluded that their work was crucial throughout the entire transition process. Aligning with the study of Kivimaa et al. (2019), the Lab. Città Corviale as an intermediary engages in activities such as facilitating experimentation and identifying requirements during the predevelopment phase, then progressing to gathering knowledge, pooling resources, establishing networks, and enhancing institutional support and capacity during the following phases (Kilelu et al., 2011). The group was constituted by a group of researchers from Roma Tre University and oversees the social support for the families being relocated in the free floor and constitutes an innovative experience that merges both technical and academic knowledge with long-term experience on the site (Caudo 2022). The Lab. Città Corviale has also developed part of the initiatives of the PUI, repeating the strategies of the Contratto Quartiere II on different parts of the complex, such as the change of use from commercial to residential, now applied to the 'VI lot', and the social support tasks developed by the Lab. Over the years, the Lab has acted as a bridge between the social approach of the Contratto de Quartiere II and the integrated approach of the PUI. The establishment of the Lab. Città Corviale was originally linked to the change of use of the free floor, however, since its inception, the Lab has accumulated a wealth of knowledge on the territory, which proved highly significant and valuable when responding to the call of the PUI in 2021.

Concluding remarks of this article

This article takes the case of Corviale to study the nexus between the lifespan of housing estates and new environmental policies in the context of housing estate regeneration initiatives. The study proposes an alternative approach to analysing housing estate's governance by tracing both physical factors and socio-political decisions and paying attention to how these two factors relate to each other. Additionally, this study explores how climate change politics can catalyse government-driven social innovation initiatives within housing estates.

To achieve this, the study first describes the physical characteristics of the housing estate, pointing out the mismatching physical results of Corviale with the planners' initial intentions. This physical analysis nourishes the development of the lifecycle reconstruction of Corviale,

that traces the main policies and initiatives that have contributed to either enlarging or reducing the lifespan of the housing estate. The lifecycle method involves mapping out the main physical transformation events at Corviale, the achievements of the work of local community groups that have taken place on site, and the top-down actions from housing, local, and regional authorities developed on site. The results of the lifecycle analysis present how the physical characteristic of Corviale have influenced the evolution of the housing estate towards both the reduction and the enlargement of its lifespan. However, as developed through the article, some sociotechnical relations, such as the relation between the morphology regulation instrument *Carta Per la Qualita*, have paved the way towards the long-term regeneration of the housing estate.

The long-term regeneration process of Corviale is studied through the analysis of its two main regeneration programs, the Contratto de Quartiere II and the PUI plan. The analysis of the programs shows how both combine social innovation measures with environmental goals. Comparing the environmental approaches of the two plans highlights a significant increase in attention to ecological aspects from the Contratto de Quartiere II, approved in 2003, to the PUI, approved in 2022. These results also highlight how the Contratto di Quartiere II experimented with some social innovation initiatives developed by intermediary groups, that were later consolidated through the larger investment provided by the PUI plan; through the PNRR and the NGEU funds. Initially developed by the Corviale Territorial Laboratory led by the Comune di Roma, social innovation initiatives were later continued by the Lab. Città Corviale, appointed by the Lazio Region and dependent from Roma Tre university. The analysis of the two regeneration programs of Corviale indicates how the intermediary groups, initially appointed by local or regional authorities, have developed social support tasks within the housing estate and have connected the social approaches of Contratto de Quartiere II with those of the PUI plan. The work of this initiatives has entered into the larger constellation of social innovation initiatives that have historically taken place at Corviale, with the difference than in this case, such initiatives are government-driven instead of bottom up.

Social innovation initiatives in Corviale encompass the community support activities, social mobilisation, data gathering and documentation that has been carried out by multiple local associations, community groups and research institutions since the opening of the building. These initiatives have been developed by both grassroots organisations and by government-driven arrangements. Although Corviale has a rich history of grassroots initiatives, this study has focused on the social innovation actions that have been fostered by institutional arrangements, fitted within the framework of the two urban regeneration programs Contratto de Quartiere II and the Piano Urbano Integrato (PUI - PNRR). By studying how government driven social innovation can be fuelled through the funding of housing estate regeneration programs with environmental budget, the study intends to contribute to the literature that approaches the government's role in social innovation processes (Bragaglia, 2020) and align with the ideas presented in the SI "Place based Just

Transition”, which explores how place-based energy transition policies and practices can support processes of social innovation (Bragaglia, 2020). The main limitation of this research lies in the ongoing nature of government-driven social innovation initiatives. As these initiatives continue to unfold, further study will be necessary to revisit and evaluate their long-term effects. A future review will offer the necessary time distance to assess the impact of these initiatives within the framework of government-led arrangements.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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